

An Evaluation of UTM ConOps for Drone Deliveries: From Pre-Planned Air Corridors to Dynamic 4D Trajectories

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Abstract—Efficient Unmanned Aircraft System Traffic Management (UTM) is crucial for scaling low-altitude logistic and transportation operations. This research evaluates three UTM Concepts of Operations (ConOps) with varying airspace organization: ConOps A uses non-overlapping air corridors, ConOps B allows intersecting air corridors, and ConOps C enables free flights with dynamic 4D trajectory management.

A simulation-based assessment framework examined these ConOps across different scenarios, evaluating metrics related to safety, business operations, flight logistics, and UTM system factors. The simulations covered various urban environments and delivery patterns, from high-rise dense areas to sparse low-rise regions, including hub-to-multiple-destinations and hub-to-hub movements.

Results show that ConOps A achieves highest safety but lowest efficiency and flexibility. ConOps C provides maximum efficiency and adaptability but requires substantial computational resources and faces increased safety challenges with higher traffic volumes. ConOps B demonstrates balanced performance. These findings provide insights for implementing UTM ConOps in urban drone delivery applications.

Keywords—Traffic management; UTM; drone delivery; Concept of Operations; air corridor; 4D trajectory planning;

I. INTRODUCTION

Commercial services that utilize Unmanned Aircraft Systems (UAS) are expected to grow rapidly. These services cover a variety of applications, such as drone deliveries (Lemardelé et al., 2021), search and rescue, emergency response, and leisure activities (Liu et al., 2015). Examples of implementations in this domain include Meituan’s execution of over 220,000 drone deliveries in Shenzhen, China, in 2023 (Meituan, 2024), healthcare services by Antwork Robotics, and operations by Zipline’s autonomous drones. The latter have collectively covered more than 70 million miles and delivered more than 10 million items across four continents, among other initiatives.

An important enabler for expanding air mobility and drone logistics is UAS Traffic Management (UTM), which ensures the secure and efficient functioning of unmanned aircraft. UTM is also known as Air Traffic Control (ATC) services

or Air Traffic Management (ATM) for managing UAS operations in low-altitude airspace. Several national-level R&D UTM initiatives have proposed various Concepts of Operations (ConOps) (EUROCONTROL, 2019; FAA, 2023). These ConOps primarily vary in terms of airspace structuring and the emphasis on pre-flight planning versus in-flight adjustments. Such differences, combined with varying Communication, Navigation, and Surveillance (CNS) conditions, can lead to substantial variations in the safety, reliability, and scalability of air mobility and drone logistics. Thus, the purpose of this paper is to evaluate the effectiveness of various ConOps, due primarily to the diverse configurations of airspace.

A. National/Regional UTM R&D Programs

The integration of UAS into existing airspace requires the development of specialized airspace management frameworks with appropriate rules and standards to ensure safe operations (Jang et al., 2017). This requirement comes from the fundamental operational differences between traditional manned aviation and UAS operations. UAS operations can significantly exceed the volume of current manned aviation, and their typical operations do not involve current onboard human pilots and air traffic control (ATC).

Several government-led UTM R&D programs have proposed a set of comprehensive ConOps to address these challenges (Bauranov & Rakas, 2021). These ConOps provide guidelines, procedures, and technologies to support the increasing integration of UAS operations. In addition, they propose various airspace structures to effectively manage UAS trajectories.

The FAA-NASA UTM program (FAA, 2021) outlines a UTM system to facilitate UAS access to low-altitude airspace (below 400 feet above ground level (AGL) (FAA, 2022) and above (FAA, 2023). This system operates on a digital platform that enables the sharing of planned flight details, ensuring uniform situational awareness for all airspace users. Within this system, the FAA provides regulatory oversight and establishes operational frameworks for UTM operations. UAS operators interact with UAS Service Suppliers (USSs), which function as intermediaries within the UTM ecosystem, assisting operators in meeting regulatory and operational requirements. USSs provide services including operational planning support,

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strategic deconfliction, and tactical deconfliction. The UTM project categorizes research into four distinct Technical Capability Levels (TCLs), each representing an increase in operational complexity. TCL4, the most advanced level, focuses on integrating multiple simultaneous low-visibility operations in urban settings through collaborative and automated UTM systems, addressing challenges such as increased obstacles and reduced lines of sight.

The European Commission’s U-space program provides a set of services that rely on high levels of digitalization and automation, along with specific procedures to support safe, efficient and secure access to airspace for large numbers of drones (EUROCONTROL, 2019; SESAR Joint Undertaking, 2023). It includes several projects, like Metropolis (Sunil et al., 2015), DLR U-Space in Germany (Geister & Korn, 2017), the Low-level Remotely Piloted Aircraft System (RPAS) Traffic Management System (LLRTM) in France (Tallec et al., 2017), etc. U-space development is staged from basic services such as visual line of sight (VLOS) operations in low-density areas (U1 U-space) to more complex beyond visual line of sight (BVLOS) operations in high-density areas, eventually integrating UTM with ATM through extensive automation (U4 U-space).

There are also other UTM programs, such as UTM programs in Singapore (Mohamed Salleh et al., 2018) and Japan (Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency (JAXA), 2017).

B. Airspace Structures in UTM ConOps

Different levels of airspace structuring have been proposed in these UTM R&D programs, and these structures rely on different strategic and tactical planning to avoid conflicts. Less structured airspaces rely on more in-flight tactical conflict resolution, and highly structured airspaces push the operations to have more pre-flight strategic planning. Typical airspace structures can be broadly grouped into corridor-based operations, zones-based operations, layers-based operations, and free-flight-based operations, as shown in Figure 1.

Corridor/tube-based operations (EUROCONTROL, 2018; FAA, 2023; Jang et al., 2017) is a highly structured approach. In this ConOps, fixed route structures are established well in advance. Drone operations are restricted to following the tubes in airspace. In FAA-NASA UTM, air corridors can be spatially separated or temporally separated, as shown in Figure 1d.

For zone-based operations, airspace is divided into zones, with aircraft assigned to specific zones based on their characteristics and flight directions. This approach aims to group similar operations together (Sunil et al., 2015). In U-space, geofencing, geocaging, and geovectoring technologies are proposed to support these airspace structures. Geofencing defines no-go areas for drones, geocaging keeps a group of drones in a part of the airspace, and geovectoring further adds the geovector intervals of speed as an additional limitation (Hoekstra et al., 2018).

Similar to zone-based operations, the layers segment airspace into distinct altitude bands, each associated with specific heading ranges. This approach aims to reduce potential

conflicts by separating aircraft according to their direction of travel (Hoekstra et al., 2016; Vlaskin et al., 2024).

Free flight/full mix (Sunil et al., 2015) is the least structured approach. The individual aircraft is responsible for tactical collision avoidance. Each aircraft independently calculates and executes an optimal trajectory, resolving conflicts through real-time maneuvers such as cruising, climbing, or descending (Sunil et al., 2015).

II. EXPERIMENT DESIGN

A. Representative UTM ConOps (the independent variable)

This study aims to assess the performance of three distinct ConOps for urban drone deliveries in specific scenarios, as illustrated in Figure 2. Each ConOps represents a different approach to airspace structure and traffic management for trajectory planning:

- Concept A requires pre-planned corridors with no spatial intersection;
- Concept B utilizes pre-planned corridors that allow intersections;
- Concept C supports real-time, dynamically planned 4D trajectories without pre-planned corridors.

These concepts vary in their flexibility, infrastructure requirements, and management complexity.

Figure 3 illustrates the simulation-based assessment method developed to evaluate these ConOps in various scenarios. The method comprises two primary steps:

- 1) Flight Plan Generation: Built-in supporting traffic management algorithms, including corridor planning and trajectory planning algorithms, generate 4D trajectories for drones according to each ConOps’ design requirements.
- 2) UAV Traffic Simulation: A simplified Monte Carlo simulation models uncertainties in trajectory execution, generating actual 4D trajectories.

Following these steps, evaluation metrics are calculated for comparative analysis.

The comparison in this study emphasizes the impacts of airspace structures and traffic management strategies on system performance, rather than focusing on specific planning algorithm implementations. The selected algorithms and parameter settings represent commonly used methodologies in the field, ensuring comparability across the three ConOps.

B. Evaluation Metrics

Seven indicators are used as evaluation metrics to assess the performance of different UTM ConOps in four aspects: safety, business, operations and the UTM system. These indicators are summarized in Table I.

Safety is of utmost importance in the UTM system, which encompasses the protection of unmanned aircraft, the public, and infrastructure. Loss of separation (n_{LoS}) is used here as a basic measure of safety, which tracks instances where drones violate minimum safe separation distances in their actual 4D trajectories. Let D_{min} be the minimum required horizontal separation distance and H_{min} be the minimum required vertical separation. Both D_{min} and H_{min} were set

(a) Full mix, layers, zones, tubes (Sunil et al., 2015)

(b) Sky-lanes (Jang et al., 2017)

(c) Corridors (FAA, 2020)

(d) Temporal and spatial separated air corridors (FAA, 2023)

Figure 1: Example of different airspace structures

Figure 2: Three distinct UTM ConOps

as 10m in this study, chosen as a conservative and practical baseline reflecting expected GNSS accuracy and commonly assumed separation distances in UTM simulations. For drones i and j at time t , the loss of separation is defined as

$$x_{i,j,t} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } |h_{i,t} - h_{j,t}| < H_{min} \text{ or } |d_{i,t} - d_{j,t}| < D_{min}, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

The total number of loss-of-separation events n_{LoS} is then calculated as

$$n_{LoS} = \sum_{t=0}^T \sum_{i,j \in [N_t], i \neq j} x_{i,j,t}. \quad (2)$$

Other safety performance, such as the ability to handle unexpected events, such as system failures or unexpected entry into restricted airspace, is not considered.

From a business standpoint, UTM features have a direct effect on delivery operations, affecting fleet management and order fulfillment. We employ the **delivery failure rate** (γ_{df}) indicator, reflecting the percentage of unfulfilled orders. In this study, if a conflict-free route cannot be assigned to an order during the planning phase—due to spatial constraints or capacity saturation—the order is considered undeliverable and contributes to the failure rate. For each order o , let y_o denote whether the order can be delivered:

$$y_o = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if order } o \text{ cannot be delivered,} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

The delivery failure rate γ_{df} is then calculated as:

$$\gamma_{df} = \sum_{o \in [O]} y_o / |O|. \quad (4)$$

Figure 3: An Evaluation of UTM ConOps for Drone Deliveries: From Pre-Planned Air Corridors to Dynamic 4D Trajectories

Meanwhile, we employ the **delivery delay rate** (γ_{od}) indicator, reflecting the percentage of delayed orders. For each order o , let z_o denote whether the order is delayed:

$$z_o = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if order } o \text{ is delayed,} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

The delivery delay rate γ_{od} is then calculated as:

$$\gamma_{od} = \sum_{o \in [O]} z_o / |O|. \quad (4)$$

Operational efficiency reflects the capability of a system to reduce detours and delays. For measuring operational efficiency, we utilize the **flight time ratio** (γ_t) and **flight distance ratio** (γ_d):

$$\gamma_t = \sum_{o \in [O]} t_o^p / \sum_{o \in [O]} t_o^d \quad (5)$$

$$\gamma_d = \sum_{o \in [O]} d_o^p / \sum_{o \in [O]} d_o^d, \quad (6)$$

where t_o^d and d_o^d represent the minimal flight time and distance for order o , while t_o^p and d_o^p denote the actual flight time and distance. These ratios assist in standardizing variations across different scenario scales and center the analysis on the ConOps.

From the standpoint of UTM performance evaluation by regulators, airspace occupancy and the necessary computational resources to facilitate large-scale operations are key metrics. Airspace occupancy (V_x) and computational time (t_c) are leveraged to evaluate the UTM system's efficacy. The airspace occupancy metric is defined as the proportion of airspace occupied for more than x duration:

$$V_x = \sum_{g \in [G], t_g > x} g / |G|, \quad (7)$$

where t_g is the cumulative time drones occupy grid cell g . In the scenario where $x = 0$, V_0 represents the portion of airspace utilized by at least one drone.

The computational time (t_c) is calculated by the total running time t_I of the UTM Implementation module for each ConOp.

C. Testing Scenarios

The experiment evaluates various ConOps using four delivery scenarios, defined by combinations of urban density and order flow patterns, with an unlimited aircraft fleet assumed: **Scenario 1**: dense environment with hub-to-destination deliveries, **Scenario 2**: dense environment with hub-to-hub deliveries, **Scenario 3**: sparse environment with hub-to-destination deliveries, **Scenario 4**: sparse environment with hub-to-hub deliveries.

Two contrasting urban environments:

- **Dense Urban Setting**: Mong Kok in Hong Kong SAR, characterized by high density high-rise buildings.
- **Sparse Urban Setting**: Delft in the Netherlands, exemplifying a sparsely populated landscape with low-rise structures.

Figure 4 depicts these environments across various altitude layers. Mong Kok spans an area of 2 km by 2 km with building heights between 0 and 200 meters, whereas Delft extends over 5 km by 6.5 km, with most structures under 40 meters. For standardization purposes, a 2 km by 2 km section in Delft is selected. In both areas, the flyable layer is set at 60 to 120 meters above the ground.

Two common delivery scenarios examined in the study (as shown in Figure 5):

- **Hub-to-destination deliveries**: These involve distribution from a commercial hub to surrounding locales, with peak times at 12 pm and 6 pm, aligning with lunch and dinner hours over the operational day (8 am to 10 pm);
- **Hub-to-hub deliveries**: Involving transport between two commercial or healthcare hubs, these occur evenly throughout the operational period (9 am to 9 pm).

D. Control Variables

This study uses a controlled experimental approach to assess the performance of various ConOps in different drone

Evaluation categories	Indicators	Equations
Safety	loss of separation	$n_{LoS} = \sum_{t=0}^T \sum_{i,j \in [N_t], i \neq j} x_{i,j,t}$
Business	delivery failure rate	$\gamma_{df} = \sum_{o \in [O]} y_o / O $
	delivery delay rate	$\gamma_{od} = \sum_{o \in [O]} z_o / O $
Operations	flight time ratio	$\gamma_t = \sum_{o \in [O]} t_o^p / \sum_{o \in [O]} t_o^d$
	flight distance ratio	$\gamma_d = \sum_{o \in [O]} d_o^p / \sum_{o \in [O]} d_o^d$
UTM system	airspace occupancy	$V_x = \sum_{g \in [G], t_g > x} g/G$
	computational time	$t_c = t_I$

TABLE I. Summary of evaluation metrics

Figure 4: Scenario set-up: urban environment

Figure 5: Scenario set-up: order characteristics

delivery scenarios. The following parameters act as control variables to clarify the relationships between the ConOps design (independent variable) and the evaluation metrics (dependent variables).

- **Traffic Volume and Complexity:** The volume of traffic is directly proportional to the number of orders O . However, traffic complexity depends on the total number of vertiports M and orders O , influencing both the spatial (number of vertiports) and temporal (real-time order count) dimensions of traffic complexity.
- **Order Volume and Uncertainty:** The volume of orders is determined by the number of orders O . Uncertainty is measured by the proportion of orders with origin or destination at unknown destinations, those not accounted for by aggregated orders during planning.
- **Airspace Management Resolution:** Managed by the resolution of grid cells, which has a direct impact on the computational intricacy of the ConOps.

Table II presents the baseline values and ranges for sensitivity analysis for each of these parameters. By systematically varying these parameters, we can evaluate the performance and robustness of each ConOps across a range of realistic drone delivery scenarios. To quantify the operational complexity of a given scenario, we define a composite metric that incorporates both the number of vertiports and the number of real-time delivery orders. The traffic complexity C is calculated as:

$$\text{Complexity} = \lambda \cdot N \cdot \log_{10} \left(\frac{N}{V} \right) \quad (8)$$

where N represents the number of active delivery orders and V denotes the number of vertiports available for routing and scheduling. This formulation accounts for both the scale of the system (through N) and its traffic density (through N/V). The logarithmic scaling ensures that the complexity increases sub-linearly with density, avoiding disproportionate inflation of the metric in high-load scenarios. .

III. UTM SIMULATION

A. Implementation of UTM ConOps A, B, C

A set of 3D corridor and 4D trajectory planning algorithms supports the implementation of ConOps A, B, and C. While constraints differ among the concepts, the algorithms are designed for comparability. Figure 6 illustrates the algorithms used for each ConOps. These algorithms primarily comprise the following modules:

- 1) **Graph Construction:** Discretizes the environment into searchable 3D or 4D grid graphs.
- 2) **Corridor Design:** Generates air corridors tailored to each ConOps, either spatially separated or allowing intersections.
- 3) **4D Trajectory Planning:** Outputs conflict-free 4D trajectories based on each ConOps's requirements.

1) *Implementation of ConOps A:* ConOps A requires pre-planned, unidirectional corridors without intersections. The process includes:

- 1) Discretization of urban environments into 3D grid cells.
- 2) Generating spatially separated corridors using aggregated orders.
- 3) Allocating drones to these corridors and generating 4D trajectories for real-time orders.

If real-time orders exceed corridor capacity, additional corridors are generated. Temporal scheduling is unnecessary as trajectories are spatially separated. Orders without conflict-free trajectories cannot be serviced.

2) *Implementation of ConOps B:* ConOps B allows for pre-planned unidirectional corridors with intersections, but the 4D trajectories for drones are still constrained by these pre-planned corridors. The implementation process includes the following.

- 1) Discretization of urban environments into 3D grid cells.
- 2) Generating air corridors using aggregated orders.
- 3) Applying 4D planning for temporal scheduling and conflict-free trajectories.

Corridors must avoid opposite-direction overlaps. Trajectory planning in ConOps B is event-driven, using the 4D planning algorithm on grid cells within pre-planned corridors. Existing trajectories are treated as moving obstacles. For each real-time order, a new 4D grid graph is created by extending corridor airspace along the time dimension, starting at the order event time (Figure 7).

3) *Implementation of ConOps C:* ConOps C adopts a "free flight operations" approach, allowing drones to navigate along preferred trajectories without reliance on pre-planned corridors, but the trajectory cannot be modified in flight once it is sent to the drone. The implementation involves:

- 1) Real-time 4D trajectory planning on dynamic grid graphs.
- 2) Constructing a 4D grid graph for each order, encompassing all flyable zones.
- 3) Using temporal delays or rerouting to mitigate conflicts.

In ConOps C, each 4D grid graph encompasses all flyable zones in the environment, contrasting with ConOps B, where only the airspace inside the corridors is available. In both ConOps B and C, the timestep for 4D planning is set at 3 seconds, with a total duration of 20 minutes for each 4D grid graph.

B. Traffic Simulation

After generating the air corridors and planned trajectories via the implementation of UTM ConOps A, B and C, a Monte Carlo simulation is conducted to insert uncertainties into the planned trajectories and simulate actual trajectories. Although strategic deconfliction is applied, the Monte Carlo model includes real-world execution uncertainties (e.g., communications, navigation, and surveillance systems), which can cause slight trajectory drift and result in residual loss-of-separation events.

In this simplified Monte Carlo simulation, Gaussian noise is added to each waypoint of the planned 4D trajectories. For a **planned 4D trajectory** represented as:

$$x_t^p = \{\dots, (p_l, t_l), \dots, (p_m, t_m), \dots, (p_n, t_n), \dots\},$$

where (p_m, t_m) is a 4D waypoint indicating its position and time, we add noise that follows a Gaussian distribution $\Delta \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 2.5)$. This distribution ensures that 95% of the noise values fall within a radius of 5 meters from the planned position. The resulting **actual 4D trajectory** is then represented as:

$$x_t^a = \{\dots, (p_l + \Delta_l, t_l), \dots, (p_m + \Delta_m, t_m), \dots, (p_n + \Delta_n, t_n), \dots\},$$

This simulation approach allows for a realistic representation of the uncertainties in UAV operations, providing a more accurate basis for evaluating the performance of different ConOps in real-world drone delivery scenarios.

IV. EXPERIMENT RESULTS

A. Flight Trajectories Resulted in ConOps A, B, and C

The experimental results compare the performance of the three ConOps under 60 vertiports and 2,000 orders (Figure 8). ConOps A used all altitude layers but relied on 42 fixed corridors, limiting successful deliveries to orders aligned with these rigid pathways. This highlights the constraints of nonintersecting corridor designs in dense vertiport scenarios. ConOps B, with controlled intersections, delivered all orders using a single altitude layer, showing greater spatial efficiency. ConOps C, employing dynamic 4D trajectory planning without fixed corridors, also achieved full order fulfillment with a single altitude layer. These results demonstrate the superior scalability and flexibility of ConOps B and C compared to the rigid design of ConOps A.

Experiment parameters	Factors	Baseline	Sensitivity analysis
Traffic Complexity	# of vertiports \times # of real-time orders	20 \times 5000	[10 \times 2000, 10 \times 6000, 10 \times 10000, 40 \times 2000, 40 \times 6000, 40 \times 10000, 60 \times 2000, 60 \times 6000, 60 \times 10000]
Order Volume and Uncertainty	# of real-time orders	5000	[100, 2000, 4000, 6000, 8000, 10000]
	Ratio of unknown vertiports ¹	0%	[0%, 20%, 40%, 60%, 80%, 100%]
Airspace Management Resolution	Grid cell resolution	10m \times 10m \times 10m	[2m \times 2m \times 2m, 5m \times 5m \times 5m, 10m \times 10m \times 10m]

¹ real-time orders that are not covered by aggregated orders are from unknown vertiports

TABLE II. Experiment parameters and their values for baseline testing and sensitivity analysis

Figure 6: Algorithms for each ConOps

Figure 7: The 4D grid graph

B. Baseline Testing Results

Baseline experiments were conducted using the default parameters in Table II, with results presented in Figures 9 through 12. Lower values across all metrics indicate better performance. While absolute values depend on specific algorithms and setups, the relative differences provide key insights into the performance of each ConOps.

- **Loss of Separation:** ConOps A recorded the fewest loss-of-separation events, demonstrating superior conflict avoidance, while ConOps B slightly exceeded ConOps

C. Hub-to-destination scenarios consistently experienced fewer events than hub-to-hub scenarios.

- **Delivery Failure and Delay Rates:** ConOps B and C achieved zero delivery failures, reflecting robust reliability. ConOps A experienced occasional failures in hub-to-destination scenarios. For delays, ConOps A had none, ConOps C had minimal delays in hub-to-destination scenarios, and ConOps B recorded the highest delay rates.
- **Flight Time and Distance Ratios:** ConOps A had the highest flight time and distance ratios, followed by ConOps B, with ConOps C achieving the lowest. Differences were minimal, indicating efficient corridor designs across all ConOps.
- **Airspace Occupancy:** ConOps B demonstrated the lowest airspace occupancy, showcasing efficiency. ConOps A had the highest occupancy in hub-to-hub scenarios, while ConOps C peaked in hub-to-destination scenarios due to varying spatial demand patterns.
- **Computational Time:** ConOps A required the least computational time, with ConOps C requiring the most, particularly in hub-to-hub scenarios. The gap between ConOps B and C was smaller in hub-to-destination scenarios.

C. Sensitivity analysis

We conducted a sensitivity analysis by varying key parameters (Table II), focusing on Scenario 1 (dense urban

Figure 8: The flight trajectories for ConOps A, B and C in Scenario 1 (60 vertiports, 2000 real-time orders)

Figure 9: Testing results for Scenario 1 (dense environment (Mong Kok, Hong Kong SAR) with hub-to-destination deliveries)

Figure 10: Testing results for Scenario 2 (dense environment (Mong Kok, Hong Kong SAR) with hub-to-hub deliveries)

environment, point-to-destination deliveries). Key results are summarized as follows:

- **Loss of Separation Events** (Figure 13): ConOps A maintains consistently low loss-of-separation events, highlighting strong safety performance, while ConOps B and C exhibit exponential increases with rising traffic complexity, with B performing the worst. Order volume increases lead to gradual growth in events for A, but rapid, non-linear increases for B and C. ConOps A relies

on static, non-overlapping corridors, which inherently cap traffic interactions. B and C use shared or dynamic paths, where complexity and conflicts grow non-linearly. Unknown vertiport ratios have minimal impact, with A maintaining superior safety.

- **Delivery Failure and Delay Rates** (Figure 14): ConOps A shows fluctuating failure rates, reflecting inconsistency under varying complexities, while B and C achieve consistently lower rates, effectively managing uncertain-

Figure 11: Testing results for Scenario 3 (sparse environment (Delft, Netherlands) with hub-to-destination deliveries)

Figure 12: Testing results for Scenario 4 (sparse environment (Delft, Netherlands) with hub-to-hub deliveries)

ties. For delays, A performs best, followed by C, with B experiencing the highest rates due to intersection congestion.

- **Flight Time and Distance Ratios** (Figure 15): ConOps A exhibits slight increases in flight time and distance with rising order volume and unknown vertiports, indicating minor sensitivity. ConOps B and C maintain stable distance ratios, with C also achieving stable time ratios. However, B shows inefficiencies at high traffic complexity.
- **Airspace Occupancy and Computational Time** (Figure 16): ConOps B demonstrates efficient airspace usage, maintaining low occupancy, while C increases occupancy by spreading traffic. ConOps A achieves the lowest computational times, while B and C show significant increases with complexity, with C slightly outperforming B at higher levels.

The traffic complexity metric is derived from the number of vertiports and the number of real-time orders, reflecting both the spatial dispersion and the density of air traffic demand. The performance of each ConOps with respect to this complexity depends on how it handles spatial concentration and routing flexibility. ConOps A adopts a fixed airspace structure with pre-defined corridors, which makes it highly sensitive to the spatial distribution of demand. As complexity increases—typically due to more concentrated or denser orders—bottlenecks form along limited paths, resulting in sharp performance degradation. In contrast, ConOps C allows trajectory planning to be done independently for each order, dynamically computing optimized 4D trajectories. This flexible approach is far less affected by global traffic complexity, as it can always identify more efficient routes, even under high demand. Therefore, ConOps C appears less sensitive to the complexity metric, which is consistent with its design philosophy.

For granularity of airspace management, only ConOps A

Figure 13: Sensitivity Analysis of Safety Metrics

Figure 14: Sensitivity Analysis of Business Metrics

can handle grid cell resolutions of 2m x 2m x 2m and 5m x 5m. ConOps B and C need too much time to generate trajectories at these resolutions.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study presents a comparative evaluation of three distinct UTM ConOps for urban drone deliveries across

Figure 15: Sensitivity Analysis of Flight Operation Metrics

Figure 16: Sensitivity Analysis of UTM Metrics

various scenarios. ConOps A utilizes pre-planned corridors without spatial intersections; ConOps B employs pre-planned corridors with allowed intersections; ConOps C operates without pre-planned corridors, supporting real-time, dynamically planned 4D trajectories. We developed a simulation-based evaluation framework to analyze these ConOps across different urban environments and order characteristics. The methodology incorporates built-in traffic management algorithms, including corridor and trajectory planning algorithms, to generate 4D trajectories that meet the specific design requirements of each ConOps. A simplified Monte Carlo simulation was then employed to account for real-world uncertainties in trajectory execution, producing actual 4D trajectories. Based on both planned and simulated trajectories, we calculated a set of evaluation metrics for comparative analysis.

Our experiments reveal distinct performance characteristics for each ConOps. ConOps A has the fewest loss-of-separation events but lacks flexibility for orders outside predefined corridors, resulting in higher flight time, distance ratios, and airspace occupancy. It compensates with minimal computational demands. ConOps C supports dynamic orders,

reducing flight time, distance, and airspace occupancy, but requires higher computational resources and has more loss-of-separation events. ConOps B shows balanced performance across most metrics, with moderate flexibility and computational demands.

Based on our simulation results, no single ConOps emerges as universally optimal, but each exhibits distinct trade-offs that inform broader UTM strategy decisions. ConOps A is preferable in contexts where safety and predictability are paramount, such as early-stage deployments or constrained urban corridors, due to its low conflict rate and minimal system requirements. ConOps C, with its support for fully dynamic routing, aligns better with long-term visions of UTM, where system intelligence and real-time adaptability are more mature, though at the cost of higher computational demands and separation risks. ConOps B strikes a middle ground and may be best suited for transitional deployment, offering scalability with acceptable performance. These findings suggest that a phased or hybrid approach to UTM architecture—adapting ConOps models to operational maturity and mission type—may be most practical in real-world implementation.

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